

SITE	YEAR	AREA	SECTOR	ELEVATION	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT	
GPR	11	B		Min: 62.586 Max: 62.968	1477 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	

In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No	Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 1837-41	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:
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DEFINITION Layer below tufo floor 1396	Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1396	Fills <input type="checkbox"/> SU:	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:
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HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compaction	FORMATION PROCESS <input type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition
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INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are			SOIL/MATRIX
Anthropic	Geological	Organic	clay ___% silt ___% sand ___%
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Glass	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)	<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)	<input type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive
			Compaction
			<input type="checkbox"/> Hard <input type="checkbox"/> Compact <input type="checkbox"/> Friable <input type="checkbox"/> Loose <input type="checkbox"/> Soft
			Color
			<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input type="checkbox"/> Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown <input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White <input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red <input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)

UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)	Depth: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original
Northern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Southern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Western Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	
Eastern Limit <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit	

STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE	
Is equal to:	Is bound to (only for masonry):
Is abutted by:	Abuts:
Is covered by: 1396, 1327	Covers: 1443, 1394, 1455
Is cut by: 1419, 1421, plough marks	Cuts:
Is filled by:	Fills: (Room N06)

OBSERVATIONS
Excavation done after first single layer of tufo stones was removed, believe there will be another stone layer directly below, cut by ploughing at the top

DESCRIPTION
Position within sector: southern corner on western side; south-west corner
Shape: floor condition degraded; shape is irregular much like previous above Su 1396, less patchy

For layers complete this section: completing this section as well for floor feature
Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): Slopes slightly to western corner of Area
Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope): Tufo stone, prep layer
Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): ~ 10-15cm
Nature of the interface with layer below: sharp diffuse commingled other (specify)

Handwritten signature or initials at the bottom of the page.

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Incomplete floor layer,
cut by possible door -
way which is below
latest Tufo floor layer.

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

See front sketch

INTERPRETATION

This layer lies directly below 1396, orange tufo floor which was badly degraded. Soil below floor shows evidence of a second tufo stone layer to complete floor as well as a prep layer. 1477 lies above an earlier tufo floor as seen in cross section of room No 6 along west edge of wall 1390. As seen in sketch, this layer may also be cut by a doorway.

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by **AMB**

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Revised by **CHN**

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PDFd by **BCR**

on **27/7/2011**

Entered by

on